

1 **Mxra8 and Mxra5 functions in lineage commitment in the human embryo.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Mxra8
8 and Mxra5 as lineage commitment factors or lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem
9 cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Zhang, R., Kim, A.S., Fox, J.M., Nair, S., Basore, K., Klimstra, W.B., Rimkunas, R., Fong, R.H.,
12 Lin, H., Poddar, S. and Crowe Jr, J.E., 2018. Mxra8 is a receptor for multiple arthritogenic alphaviruses.
13 Nature, 557(7706), pp.570-574.

14 2. Zimmerman, O., Zimmerman, M.I., Raju, S., Nelson, C.A., Errico, J.M., Madden, E.A., Holmes,
15 A.C., Hassan, A.O., VanBlargan, L.A., Kim, A.S. and Adams, L.J., 2023. Vertebrate-class-specific binding
16 modes of the alphavirus receptor MXRA8. Cell, 186(22), pp.4818-4833.